

Data sets for acoustic mode decomposition in ducts

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Introduction

Acoustic duct mode decomposition is a common procedure used in duct aeroacoustic, for example, during the development of aero engines and duct liners, where researchers are often tasked to create decomposition routines and measurement protocols as a first step. From my experience, creating and verifying those routines can be a tedious job, as errors from the measurement setup, data acquisition, probe calibration, and data pre-processing only become apparent after running the data through the decomposition routines. It is then often unclear if the malfunction is due to the decomposition routines or the measurement protocols.

I am providing these two datasets to facilitate the development of mode decomposition algorithms. The measurements were conducted using a carefully constructed and validated measurement setup at the Marcus Wallenberg Laboratory for Sound and Vibration Research at KTH in Stockholm, Sweden under the supervision of Prof. Mats Åbom. Along with the data, I also provide working examples of mode decomposition with the package Acdecom in the scripting language Python [1].

Data sets

Empty duct with higher order modes

The data can be downloaded as a single machine readable file¹.

We measured the propagation of higher order acoustic modes along an empty circular duct section, employing a combination of 24 microphones and 16 sources. The microphones and sources were divided into two sets, before and after the empty duct section, as depicted in Figure 1. With this setup, we could excite and resolve the first 6 duct modes. Additional information regarding the configuration, data analysis, and outcomes can be found in Ref. [1]. The data set corresponds to the results shown in Figure 12 of this reference.

Figure 1: Experimental setup for acquiring the data set. From Ref. [2].

The dataset includes pressure readings for each microphone at specific frequencies, with each loudspeaker being used individually. The tutorial section of the Acdecom Python

¹ <https://github.com/ssackMWL/acdecom/blob/master/examples/data/higherOrderModes.txt>

package provides a comprehensive description of the post-processing, including the experiment's parameters².

Liner in a rectangular flow duct

The data can be downloaded as a single machine readable file³.

We measured the transmission loss of a duct silencer in a rectangular duct, employing a combination of 6 microphones and 4 sources. The microphones and sources were divided into two sets, before and after the liner duct section. Additional information regarding the configuration, data analysis, and outcomes can be found in Ref. [3]. The data set corresponds to the results shown in Figure 12 of this reference. The tutorial section of the Acdecom Python package provides a comprehensive description of the post-processing, including the experiment's parameters⁴.

References

- [1] Sack S. acdecom—A Python module for acoustic wave decomposition in flow ducts. *Software Impacts* 2020;6:100025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpa.2020.100025>.
- [2] Sack S, Åbom M, Efraimsson G. On acoustic multi-port characterisation including higher order modes. *Acta Acustica United with Acustica* 2016;102:834–50. <https://doi.org/10.3813/AAA.918998>.
- [3] Yang C, Zhang P, Jacob S, Trigell E, Åbom M. Investigation of Extended-Tube Liners for Control of Low-Frequency Duct Noise. *AIAA Journal* 2021;59:4179–94. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J059988>.

² https://acdecom.readthedocs.io/en/latest/auto_examples/plot_higherOrderModes.html#sphx-glr-auto-examples-plot-higherordermodes-py

³ <https://github.com/ssackMWL/acdecom/blob/master/examples/data/liner.txt>

⁴ https://acdecom.readthedocs.io/en/latest/auto_examples/plot_liner.html#sphx-glr-auto-examples-plot-liner-py